

PREDICTION OF MULTIPLE PLY CRACKING IN GENERAL SYMMETRIC LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Predictive techniques for damage development in general symmetric laminates require a reliable methodology for dealing with the progressive formation of discrete ply cracks in multiple plies of the laminate. For laminates subject to general in-plane loading and thermal residual stresses, and when ply cracking occurs in just a single orientation, an accurate stress transfer model has already been developed. This model has now been extended so that ply cracking in multiple orientations can be analysed approximately using an homogenisation technique. The objective of this paper is to describe the homogenisation methodology, and its application to the prediction of progressive ply crack formation in multiple plies of any symmetric laminate. The approach uses the analysis, for ply cracks having a single orientation, as the basis for the homogenisation procedure that is designed to determine all the effective homogenised thermo-elastic constants of the discretely cracked ply. These homogenised properties are then used in conjunction with undamaged laminate analysis to predict properties for a damaged laminate having ply cracks in any ply. The new approach to achieving the exact homogenisation of the effective properties of cracked plies in the laminate involves the introduction of a shear coupling term in the stress-strain relations that define individual homogenised ply properties. The development of progressive ply cracking methodology involves the repeated application of the homogenisation technique, and its inverse, combined with various rotations of the laminate and the applied in-plane stress field.

To illustrate the model capabilities, the homogenisation analysis, and ply cracking methodology, are applied to the uniaxial loading of a modified $[55/-55]_8$ GRP laminate that is designed to exhibit progressive ply cracking. One important result is the discontinuous behaviour of the stress-strain curve, even when the fracture energy for ply cracking is not subject to statistical variability. This arises because ply crack events are distributed in a number of different plies. It is, however, shown that the analysis predicts a smooth dependence of the effective laminate properties on the average ply crack density. One key result is that the model can in principle predict the strength of the laminate for some laminate types (especially those for which there are no 0° plies). The reason for this is that the maximum stress applied during loading occurs at a relatively low level of ply cracking; most laminate damage occurring during the catastrophic failure of the laminate.

Key Terms: Polymer-based fibre reinforced composites, General symmetric laminates, Multiple ply cracking, Thermo-elastic constants, Laminate strength.

INTRODUCTION

For general symmetric laminates subject to general in-plane loading and thermal residual stresses, McCartney [1] developed a stress transfer model for ply cracking that occurs in a single orientation. Limited validation of model predictions for this case with finite element analysis (FEA) and experimental observations [2, 3] has indicated that the model is capable of: i) accurately representing the local stress distributions in damaged laminates, ii) predicting the property degradation of laminates

caused by ply cracking, and iii) the progressive formation of ply cracking during loading. In order that the existing model [1] has opportunities for much wider application in design, it has been further developed so that ply cracking in more than one orientation can be modelled. Predictive methods for damage development in composite laminates require techniques for dealing with the progressive formation of discrete ply cracks in multiple plies of a laminate. The development of a reliable stress transfer model, in the presence of discrete sets of ply cracks, is an unsolved problem that is highly likely to remain so for many years due to the mathematical complexity that is involved when applying boundary conditions to ply cracks having a variety of different orientations. The prime objective of this paper is to describe an alternative approach that is based on an homogenisation methodology that involves smoothing the effective properties of a cracked ply in a laminate into the equivalent properties of an homogeneous ply having reduced properties such that the discretely cracked laminate and its homogenised representation have identical in-plane properties. The problem is to determine all the effective homogenised thermo-elastic constants of a discretely cracked ply, so that when these properties are used in conjunction with undamaged laminate analysis to predict laminate properties, the precise properties of the damaged laminate are obtained. This type of approach can be handled using the existing methodology [1, 2] that deals only with ply cracking in a single orientation, by applying rotations to the laminate, and transformations to the applied stresses, so that the discretely cracked ply is in a 90° orientation enabling the direct application of the techniques described in [1].

There is some similarity between this approach and an earlier approach known as the ‘Equivalent Constraint Model’ (ECM) developed by Fan and Zhang [4], and further developed by Zhang et al [5, 6]. The ECM model is designed to account for the effect of neighbouring plies on the homogenised properties of a cracked ply, and crack formation in that ply. The methodology makes use of shear-lag stress transfer models when estimating the in-situ damage effective function that describes the constraint effects. In this paper, a more accurate stress-transfer model is used, together with a new approach to the homogenisation of the effective properties of cracked plies, which involves the introduction of a shear coupling term for individual ply properties. It is essential for this type of a term to be included in the analysis if precise homogenised ply properties for a cracked ply are to be determined, such that the homogenised model of the laminate has exactly the same in-plane properties as the laminate, where the cracks in the ply being homogenised are modelled as discrete entities.

GEOMETRY AND BASIC FIELD EQUATIONS

The problem under consideration concerns the triaxial deformation of a symmetric multi-layered laminate of length $2L$ and width $2W$ constructed of $2N+2$ perfectly bonded layers that can have any combination of orientations provided that there is symmetry about the mid-plane of the laminate. Ply refinement techniques need to be used so that through-thickness variations in the stress and displacement fields can adequately be modelled for each ply in the laminate. When adopting this approach, some of the layers will have identical properties. As laminate symmetry is assumed, it is necessary to consider only the upper quadrant of the right hand set of $N+1$ layers as shown in Fig.1.

A global set of rectangular Cartesian co-ordinates is chosen having the origin at the centre of the laminate. The y -direction defines the longitudinal or axial direction, the z -direction defines the in-plane transverse direction and the x -direction defines the through-thickness direction. The locations of the N interfaces in one half of the laminate ($x > 0$) are specified by $x = x_i$, $i = 1 \dots N$. The mid-plane of the laminate is specified by $x = x_0 = 0$ and the external surface by $x = x_{N+1} = h$ where $2h$ is the total thickness of the laminate. The thickness of the i^{th} layer is denoted by $h_i = x_i - x_{i-1}$. Stress, strain and displacement components, and material properties associated with the i^{th} layer are denoted by a superscript or subscript i . The orientation of the i^{th} layer is specified by the angle ϕ_i between the y -axis and the fibre direction of this layer. It is convenient to define parameters $m_i = \cos \phi_i$ and $n_i = \sin \phi_i$.

Fig. 1 : Schematic edge view of the quarter model of a multi-layer laminate

Consider the following homogenised stress-strain relations for the i^{th} layer, expressed in terms of stress and strain components referred to local coordinates (where the y' -axis is parallel with the fibres of the i^{th} ply) where stress and strain components are denoted by a prime superscript,

$$\epsilon_{xx}^{\prime i} = \frac{\sigma_{xx}^{\prime i}}{E_t^i} - \frac{\nu_a^i}{E_A^i} \sigma_{yy}^{\prime i} - \frac{\nu_t^i}{E_T^i} \sigma_{zz}^{\prime i} + \alpha_t^i \Delta T, \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{yy}^{\prime i} = -\frac{\nu_a^i}{E_A^i} \sigma_{xx}^{\prime i} + \frac{\sigma_{yy}^{\prime i}}{E_A^i} - \frac{\nu_A^i}{E_A^i} \sigma_{zz}^{\prime i} + \alpha_A^i \Delta T, \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_{zz}^{\prime i} = -\frac{\nu_t^i}{E_T^i} \sigma_{xx}^{\prime i} - \frac{\nu_A^i}{E_A^i} \sigma_{yy}^{\prime i} + \frac{\sigma_{zz}^{\prime i}}{E_T^i} + \Omega_i \sigma_{yz}^{\prime i} + \alpha_T^i \Delta T, \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_{xy}^{\prime i} = \frac{\sigma_{xy}^{\prime i}}{2\mu_a^i}, \quad \epsilon_{xz}^{\prime i} = \frac{\sigma_{xz}^{\prime i}}{2\mu_t^i}, \quad 2\epsilon_{yz}^{\prime i} = \Omega_i \sigma_{zz}^{\prime i} + \frac{\sigma_{yz}^{\prime i}}{\mu_A^i}, \quad (4)$$

where E , ν , μ and α denote Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, shear modulus and thermal expansion coefficient, and where ΔT is the uniform temperature difference defined by $\Delta T = T - T_0$ where T is the current temperature and T_0 is the temperature in the reference state for which the strain is zero and the material is everywhere stress-free (i.e. no internal or imposed external stresses). The relations (1-4) correspond to those of an orthotropic material where the fibres are parallel to the y' -axis, except that an additional term involving the shear coupling parameter Ω_i has been included in (3) and (4), such that $\Omega_i = 0$ when the laminate is undamaged. The parameter Ω_i has been introduced, as it has been shown to be essential if a ply with a distribution of discrete cracks is to homogenised precisely with regard to all in-plane thermo-elastic properties of the laminate. When the stress-strain relations (1-4) for the i^{th} layer are referred to the global coordinates of the laminate it can be shown that the resulting stress-

strain relations have the form specified in Ref. [1, eqs.(4-9)], for $i = 1 \dots N+1$, where some of the thermoelastic constants are defined by [1, eqs.(A19-A35)]. The terms that are modified by the inclusion of the damage-induced shear coupling parameter in (3) and (4) are given by

$$g_{22}^i = m_i^2 n_i^2 \left(\frac{1}{\mu_A^i} - \frac{2\nu_A^i}{E_A^i} \right) + \frac{n_i^4}{E_T^i} + \frac{m_i^4}{E_A^i} + 2m_i n_i^3 \Omega_i, \quad (5)$$

$$g_{23}^i = m_i^2 n_i^2 \left(\frac{1}{E_A^i} + \frac{1}{E_T^i} - \frac{1}{\mu_A^i} \right) - m_i^4 \frac{\nu_A^i}{E_A^i} - n_i^4 \frac{\nu_A^i}{E_A^i} + m_i n_i (m_i^2 - n_i^2) \Omega_i, \quad (6)$$

$$g_{24}^i = m_i n_i \left[(m_i^2 - n_i^2) \left(\frac{1}{\mu_A^i} - \frac{2\nu_A^i}{E_A^i} \right) - \frac{2m_i^2}{E_A^i} + \frac{2n_i^2}{E_T^i} \right] + n_i^2 (3m_i^2 - n_i^2) \Omega_i, \quad (7)$$

$$g_{33}^i = m_i^2 n_i^2 \left(\frac{1}{\mu_A^i} - \frac{2\nu_A^i}{E_A^i} \right) + \frac{m_i^4}{E_T^i} + \frac{n_i^4}{E_A^i} - 2m_i^3 n_i \Omega_i, \quad (8)$$

$$g_{34}^i = m_i n_i \left[(m_i^2 - n_i^2) \left(-\frac{1}{\mu_A^i} + \frac{2\nu_A^i}{E_A^i} \right) + \frac{2m_i^2}{E_T^i} - \frac{2n_i^2}{E_A^i} \right] + m_i^2 (m_i^2 - 3n_i^2) \Omega_i, \quad (9)$$

$$g_{44}^i = \frac{(m_i^2 - n_i^2)^2}{\mu_A^i} + 4m_i^2 n_i^2 \left(\frac{1}{E_A^i} + \frac{1}{E_T^i} + \frac{2\nu_A^i}{E_A^i} \right) + 4m_i n_i (m_i^2 - n_i^2) \Omega_i. \quad (10)$$

EDGE BOUNDARY CONDITIONS FOR UNIFORMLY CRACKED LAMINATES

Boundary conditions need to be imposed on the external edges of the uniformly cracked laminate. It is assumed that biaxial and shear loads are applied to the cracked laminate by imposing displacements on the edges of the laminate that would, in an undamaged laminate, lead to a state of combined uniform biaxial strain and uniform shear strain. Since the laminate is assumed to have length $2L$ in the y -direction and width $2W$ in the z -direction, the edge conditions for a cracked laminate are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xy} = 0, \quad v = \pm \varepsilon^c L, \quad w = \pm \gamma^c L + \varepsilon_T^c z, \quad \text{on } y = \pm L, \\ \sigma_{xz} = 0, \quad v = \varepsilon^c y, \quad w = \gamma^c y \pm \varepsilon_T^c W, \quad \text{on } z = \pm W, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where ε^c , ε_T^c and γ^c define the imposed in-plane axial, transverse and engineering shear strains for a uniformly cracked laminate. The external laminate faces are assumed to be subject to a uniform normal traction σ_t , and zero shear tractions.

Because applied displacements of the form (11) have been imposed on the edges of the cracked laminate, the corresponding stresses σ_{yy} , σ_{zz} and σ_{yz} , resulting from an exact elasticity analysis, will be non-uniform. Following the approach of [1], effective applied axial, transverse and shear stresses, and an effective out-of-plane transverse strain ε_t^c for a cracked laminate, are defined by the following averages

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma &= \frac{1}{4hW} \int_{-W}^W \int_{-h}^h \sigma_{yy}(x, L, z) dx dz, \quad \sigma_T = \frac{1}{4hL} \int_{-L}^L \int_{-h}^h \sigma_{zz}(x, y, W) dx dy, \\ \tau &= \frac{1}{4hW} \int_{-W}^W \int_{-h}^h \sigma_{yz}(x, L, z) dx dz = \frac{1}{4hL} \int_{-L}^L \int_{-h}^h \sigma_{yz}(x, y, W) dx dy, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\varepsilon_t^c = \frac{1}{4hLW} \int_{-L}^L \int_{-W}^W u(h, y, z) dy dz. \quad (13)$$

SOLUTION FOR UNDAMAGED LAMINATES

The solution procedure to deal with ply cracking in any ply involves the rotation of the laminate and transformation of the applied stress field so that discrete ply cracking can be analysed in the 90° ply of the rotated laminate. For a laminate in such an orientation, generalised plane strain conditions can be imposed where the fundamental assumption is that the displacement field has the following form for the transformed configuration

$$u = u(x, y), \quad v = v(x, y), \quad w = f(x, y) + \varepsilon_T^c z, \quad (14)$$

where ε_T^c is the in-plane transverse strain of the cracked laminate that has the same value in all layers. This representation is valid if ply cracks form in planes normal to the y-direction, and only if well away from the edges of the laminate (at least two laminate thicknesses).

Consider now the laminate in an *undamaged* state but subject to the same loading conditions and temperature as the cracked laminate such that the parameters σ_t , σ , τ and ε_T^c control laminate deformation. The corresponding effective through-thickness strain, effective axial strain, effective in-plane engineering shear strain and the effective in-plane transverse stress for an undamaged laminate are denoted respectively by ε_t , ε , γ and σ_T^0 . As the external faces of the undamaged laminate are assumed to be subject to a uniform normal stress σ_t and zero shear tractions, it follows that for all points in the laminate away from the laminate edges

$$\sigma_{xx}^i \equiv \sigma_t, \quad \sigma_{xy}^i \equiv 0, \quad \sigma_{xz}^i \equiv 0, \quad i = 1 \dots N+1. \quad (15)$$

It then follows from (15) that $\varepsilon_{xy}^i \equiv \varepsilon_{xz}^i \equiv 0$, and from [1, eqs.(22-24)] that

$$\varepsilon_t^i = \bar{g}_{11}^i \sigma_t + \bar{g}_{12}^i \sigma^i + \bar{g}_{14}^i \tau^i + \bar{\alpha}_1^i \Delta T + H_1^i \varepsilon_T^c, \quad (16)$$

$$\varepsilon = \bar{g}_{12}^i \sigma_t + \bar{g}_{22}^i \sigma^i + \bar{g}_{24}^i \tau^i + \bar{\alpha}_2^i \Delta T + H_2^i \varepsilon_T^c, \quad (17)$$

$$\gamma = \bar{g}_{14}^i \sigma_t + \bar{g}_{24}^i \sigma^i + \bar{g}_{44}^i \tau^i + \bar{\alpha}_4^i \Delta T + H_3^i \varepsilon_T^c, \quad (18)$$

where ε_t^i is the uniform out-of-plane strain, and where σ^i and τ^i are respectively the uniform axial and in-plane shear stresses in the i^{th} layer of the undamaged laminate, and where

$$\begin{aligned} H_1^i &= \frac{g_{13}^i}{g_{33}^i}, \quad H_2^i = \frac{g_{23}^i}{g_{33}^i}, \quad H_3^i = \frac{g_{34}^i}{g_{33}^i}, \\ \bar{g}_{11}^i &= g_{11}^i - \frac{(g_{13}^i)^2}{g_{33}^i}, \quad \bar{g}_{12}^i = g_{12}^i - \frac{g_{13}^i g_{23}^i}{g_{33}^i}, \quad \bar{g}_{14}^i = g_{14}^i - \frac{g_{13}^i g_{34}^i}{g_{33}^i}, \\ \bar{g}_{22}^i &= g_{22}^i - \frac{(g_{23}^i)^2}{g_{33}^i}, \quad \bar{g}_{24}^i = g_{24}^i - \frac{g_{23}^i g_{34}^i}{g_{33}^i}, \quad \bar{g}_{44}^i = g_{44}^i - \frac{(g_{34}^i)^2}{g_{33}^i}, \\ \bar{\alpha}_1^i &= \alpha_1^i - \frac{g_{13}^i}{g_{33}^i} \alpha_3^i, \quad \bar{\alpha}_2^i = \alpha_2^i - \frac{g_{23}^i}{g_{33}^i} \alpha_3^i, \quad \bar{\alpha}_4^i = \alpha_4^i - \frac{g_{34}^i}{g_{33}^i} \alpha_3^i. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

It follows from (12) that the effective applied axial, transverse and shear stresses are then given respectively by (identical to Ref. [1, eqs.(28-30)])

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{h} \sum_{i=1}^{N+1} h_i \sigma^i = A\varepsilon + B\varepsilon_T^c + D\gamma + F\sigma_t - P\Delta T, \quad (20)$$

$$\sigma_T^0 = \frac{1}{h} \sum_{i=1}^{N+1} h_i \sigma_T^i = B\varepsilon + C\varepsilon_T^c + E\gamma + G\sigma_t - Q\Delta T, \quad (21)$$

$$\tau = \frac{1}{h} \sum_{i=1}^{N+1} h_i \tau^i = D\varepsilon + E\varepsilon_T^c + Z\gamma + H\sigma_t - R\Delta T, \quad (22)$$

where the parameters A, B, ... are defined in [1, eqs.(31-41)]. The effective through-thickness strain for an undamaged laminate is given by

$$\varepsilon_t = \frac{1}{h} \sum_{i=1}^{N+1} h_i \varepsilon_t^i, \quad (23)$$

where ε_t^i is specified by (16). It can be shown using (16) and (23) that

$$\varepsilon_t = a\varepsilon + b\varepsilon_T^c + c\gamma + d\sigma_t + e\Delta T, \quad (24)$$

where the thermoelastic constants a, b, c, d and e are specified in Ref. [1, eqs.(44-48)]

The relations (20-22) and (24), relating the effective applied stresses σ , σ_T^0 , τ and the effective through-thickness strain ε_t to the uniform strains ε , ε_T^c , γ and the uniform through-thickness stress σ_t , enable the thermo-elastic constants referred to global coordinates to be determined for an undamaged laminate.

HOMOGENISATION PROCEDURE

Let $A_d, Z_d, B_d, C_d, \dots$ denote the thermo-elastic constants (known in principle using methods of [1]) appearing in stress-strain relations of the form (20-22) and (24) for a *damaged laminate* with discrete ply cracks only in the k^{th} ply. The parameters $\bar{A}_k, \bar{Z}_k, \bar{B}_k, \bar{C}_k, \dots$ are defined by relations of the following type, where the k^{th} term in the summation has been omitted

$$\bar{A}_k = \frac{1}{h} \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} h_i \frac{\bar{g}_{44}^i}{\bar{g}_{22}^i \bar{g}_{44}^i - (\bar{g}_{24}^i)^2} \right) + \left(\sum_{i=k+1}^{N+1} h_i \frac{\bar{g}_{44}^i}{\bar{g}_{22}^i \bar{g}_{44}^i - (\bar{g}_{24}^i)^2} \right) \right]. \quad (25)$$

Define parameters $A_k = A_d - \bar{A}_k$, $Z_k = Z_d - \bar{Z}_k$, $B_k = B_d - \bar{B}_k$, $C_k = C_d - \bar{C}_k$, ..., which are also in principle known, as the thermo-elastic constants of the damaged laminate, and those of the undamaged or previously homogenised plies, are regarded as known values when applying the homogenisation procedure to the k^{th} ply. The parameters A_k, Z_k, \dots correspond to the k^{th} terms that are omitted in relations of the type (25). The thermo-elastic constants $A_d, Z_d, B_d, C_d, \dots$ for the laminate with discrete cracks in the k^{th} ply are calculated using the analysis methods described in [1].

It can be shown that

$$\chi_k = \frac{1}{A_k Z_k - D_k^2} = \left(\frac{h}{h_k} \right)^2 \left[\frac{\bar{g}_{22}^k \bar{g}_{44}^k}{\bar{g}_{22}^k \bar{g}_{44}^k - (\bar{g}_{24}^k)^2} \right], \quad (26)$$

$$\bar{g}_{44}^k = \frac{h_k}{h} A_k \chi_k, \quad \bar{g}_{24}^k = -\frac{h_k}{h} D_k \chi_k, \quad \bar{g}_{22}^k = \frac{h_k}{h} Z_k \chi_k, \quad (27)$$

$$H_3^k = \chi_k (B_k D_k - A_k E_k), \quad H_2^k = \chi_k (D_k E_k - B_k Z_k), \quad (28)$$

$$\bar{g}_{12}^k = \chi_k (D_k H_k - F_k Z_k), \quad \bar{g}_{14}^k = \chi_k (D_k F_k - A_k H_k), \quad (29)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_2^k = \chi_k (P_k Z_k - D_k R_k), \quad \bar{\alpha}_4^k = \chi_k (R_k A_k - D_k P_k), \quad (30)$$

$$g_{33}^k = \frac{h_k}{h} \left[C_k + \chi_k (2B_k D_k E_k - Z_k B_k^2 - A_k E_k^2) \right]^{-1}, \quad (31)$$

$$H_1^k = \frac{h}{h_k} \left[-G_k - \chi_k (D_k E_k F_k - B_k F_k Z_k + B_k D_k H_k - A_k E_k H_k) \right], \quad (32)$$

$$\bar{g}_{11}^k = \frac{h}{h_k} \left[d_k - \chi_k (2D_k F_k H_k - Z_k F_k^2 - A_k H_k^2) \right], \quad (33)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_1^k = \frac{h}{h_k} \left[e_k + \chi_k (P_k (D_k H_k - F_k Z_k) + R_k (D_k F_k - A_k H_k)) \right], \quad (34)$$

$$\alpha_3^k = g_{33}^k \frac{h}{h_k} \left[Q_k + \chi_k (P_k (D_k E_k - B_k Z_k) + R_k (B_k D_k - A_k E_k)) \right]. \quad (35)$$

To compute the required thermo-elastic constants from the reduced coefficients given above, use is made of (19) so that

$$\begin{aligned} g_{13}^k &= H_1^k g_{33}^k, & g_{23}^k &= H_2^k g_{33}^k, & g_{34}^k &= H_3^k g_{33}^k, \\ g_{11}^k &= \bar{g}_{11}^k + \frac{(g_{13}^k)^2}{g_{33}^k}, & g_{12}^k &= \bar{g}_{12}^k + \frac{g_{13}^k g_{23}^k}{g_{33}^k}, & g_{14}^k &= \bar{g}_{14}^k + \frac{g_{13}^k g_{34}^k}{g_{33}^k}, \\ g_{22}^k &= \bar{g}_{22}^k + \frac{(g_{23}^k)^2}{g_{33}^k}, & g_{24}^k &= \bar{g}_{24}^k + \frac{g_{23}^k g_{34}^k}{g_{33}^k}, & g_{44}^k &= \bar{g}_{44}^k + \frac{(g_{34}^k)^2}{g_{33}^k}, \\ \alpha_1^k &= \bar{\alpha}_1^k + \frac{g_{13}^k}{g_{33}^k} \alpha_3^k, & \alpha_2^k &= \bar{\alpha}_2^k + \frac{g_{23}^k}{g_{33}^k} \alpha_3^k, & \alpha_4^k &= \bar{\alpha}_4^k + \frac{g_{34}^k}{g_{33}^k} \alpha_3^k. \end{aligned}$$

All the required thermo-elastic constants for the homogenised properties (for the transformed orientation) of the cracked k^{th} ply have thus been derived in terms of damaged laminate properties and the properties of the other plies in an undamaged state. The final stage of the homogenisation procedure is to extract from the above results the corresponding values of the thermo-elastic constants (appearing in (1-4)) of the k^{th} ply that has been homogenised. As this ply is in a 90° orientation following transformation it follows from [1] and (5-10) that

$$\begin{aligned} E_t^k &= \frac{1}{g_{11}^k}, & E_A^k &= \frac{1}{g_{33}^k}, & E_T^k &= \frac{1}{g_{22}^k}, \\ v_t^k &= -g_{12}^k E_T^k, & v_a^k &= -g_{13}^k E_A^k, & v_A^k &= -g_{23}^k E_A^k, \\ \mu_t^k &= \frac{1}{2a_{11}^k}, & \mu_a^k &= \frac{1}{2a_{22}^k}, & \mu_A^k &= \frac{1}{g_{44}^k}, & \Omega_k &= -g_{24}^k, \\ \alpha_t^k &= \alpha_1^k, & \alpha_A^k &= \alpha_3^k, & \alpha_T^k &= \alpha_2^k. \end{aligned}$$

PLY CRACKING IN MULTIPLE ORIENTATIONS

Stress transfer models and energy based methods are used to predict progressive ply cracking in a laminate where just one ply (rotated so that it is a 90° ply) contains a discrete set of ply cracks when considering the formation of a new crack in this ply. The ply cracks that might have formed in the other plies are replaced by homogenised ply properties. The homogenisation procedure has the property that the laminate when homogenised has exactly the same in-plane properties as the laminate containing discrete cracks in the ply where the last ply crack formed. This is achieved using the ply property

homogenisation methodology described above. Each ply is assumed to have a set of M equally spaced potential ply crack formation sites that are labelled successively from top to bottom by $j = 1 \dots M$. A fracture energy for ply cracking is allocated to each site, taken at random from a normal distribution defined by a mean fracture energy and a standard deviation. Each ply will have a different distribution of ply cracks. The energy-based methodology for predicting progressive ply crack formation has been described in reference [1], and the method for dealing with non-uniform ply crack formation in any ply has been described in reference [2]. These methodologies have been combined to create a new energy-based method of predicting progressive ply cracking in multiple plies of a general symmetric laminate subject to general in-plane loading.

EXAMPLE OF MODEL CAPABILITIES

It is useful to provide an example of the type of predictions that can be made by the new model. A slightly modified GRP $[55/-55]_{8s}$ laminate is considered to ensure that cracking in a number of different plies occurs during the simulation, and to emphasise the changes in thermo-elastic properties that occur when ply cracks form. The plies have thickness 0.2 mm, and the following properties

$$\begin{array}{llll}
 E_A = 45.6 \text{ GPa} & E_T = 16.2 \text{ GPa} & \nu_A = 0.278 & \nu_T = 0.4 \\
 \mu_A = 5.83 \text{ GPa} & \mu_T = 5.79 \text{ GPa} & \alpha_A = 8.6 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C} & \alpha_T = 2.64 \times 10^{-5} / ^\circ\text{C}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 2 : Results of simulation: Normalised axial stress as a function of axial strain.

The modification to the laminate specified above is to replace the central -55° ply of double thickness (0.4 mm) by a -55° ply of thickness 0.2 mm. This ensures that *all* plies in the laminate have the same thickness 0.2 mm. The total length of laminate considered is 10 mm along which just 8 equally spaced potential ply cracking sites are located within each ply. The mean fracture energy assumed is 240 J/m^2 , together with a zero standard deviation. The zero value was selected in order to avoid statistical scatter in the predictions. The temperature difference between the simulation temperature of the laminate and the stress-free temperature is -120°C . Each ply was represented by just one element (to speed up the

simulation) and 128 ply cracks were allowed to form. Fig. 2 shows the stress-strain response predicted by the simulation. The normalised stress plotted is the axial stress divided by the maximum stress. The data plotted are stresses corresponding to monotonically increasing values of the applied axial strain. When determining the next ply crack to form during loading, the simulation assumes that the laminate is unloaded immediately following the formation of the new ply crack. The next ply crack to form is often predicted to occur at an applied strain that is less than the applied strain at which the previous ply crack formed. Such events are not shown in Fig. 2, as they are taken as indicating that more than one ply crack can form at the given value of the applied strain. It is seen that following ply crack formation at a progressively increasing applied strain, the stress-strain curve exhibits a local maximum value. This arises because ply cracking is occurring in more than one ply, coupled with the fact that, following the formation of each ply crack, the laminate is effectively unloaded before predicting the stress at which the next ply crack will form. It is clear from Fig.2 that the stress-strain curve is exhibiting intermittent non-catastrophic instabilities where a few ply cracks would form instantaneously. A key observation is that the modelling of ply cracking for the laminate studied has in fact led to the prediction of the strength of the laminate. Some of the damage that is modelled occurs during the collapse of the laminate. This finding could help to develop an accurate prediction technique for the strength of some types of laminate, especially those that do not contain any 0° plies.

Fig. 3 : Normalised laminate properties as a function of the average ply crack density.

The corresponding plots for some of the normalised thermo-elastic constants of the damaged laminate as functions of the averaged ply crack density (defined as the total number of ply cracks divided by the total length of laminate that is simulated) are shown in Fig. 3. It is emphasised that when the standard deviation of the fracture energy is zero, as assumed in the simulation, the initial ply cracks form one at a time but almost at the same stress level. If the energy-based ply cracking predictions could be made exactly then there would be a characteristic initial ply crack density that would instantaneously form. An

examination of the results shown in Fig. 3 indicates that ply crack formation leads to smooth dependencies of many thermoelastic constants on the average ply crack density.

CONCLUSIONS

1. By making use of a new homogenization technique for general symmetric laminates, the thermo-mechanical effects of discrete fully developed ply cracks in one ply of a general symmetric laminate can be replaced by effective homogenized in-plane properties such that the laminate with discrete ply cracks has exactly the same in-plane properties as the homogenized laminate. This procedure enables the prediction of progressive ply crack formation, based on energy methods, in any ply of a general symmetric laminate.
2. An exact homogenization technique for a damaged laminate can be developed only if the homogenized properties of individual plies are allowed to have a shear coupling term that is normally absent when modelling discrete ply cracking having a single orientation.
3. The new model is able to predict non-linear triaxial stress-strain behaviour due to damage development, and the dependence of the thermo-elastic properties on the average ply crack density, the applied stress or strain, taking full account of the effects of thermal residual stresses. The stress-strain curve exhibits local non-catastrophic instabilities, but the dependence of the thermoelastic constants on average ply crack density is, however, smooth.
4. For the angle-ply example considered, a local maximum of the stress-strain curve is predicted that can be associated with strength of the laminate.

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REFERENCES

1. McCartney L N. Model to predict effects of triaxial loading on ply cracking in general symmetric laminates. *Comp Sci & Tech* 2000; **60**: 2255-2279. (see Errata in *Comp. Sci. & Tech.* 2002; **62**: 1273-1274).
2. McCartney L N & Schoeppner G A. Predicting the effect of non-uniform ply cracking on the thermo-elastic properties of cross-ply laminates. *Comp. Sci. & Tech.* 2002; **62**:1841-1856.
3. McCartney L N. Physically based damage models for laminated composites. Accepted for publication in *Journal of Materials: Design & Applications*, 2003.
4. Fan J & Zhang J. In-situ damage evolution and micro/macro transition for laminated composites. *Comp. Sci. Tech.* 1993; **47**: 107-118.
5. Zhang J, Fan J & Soutis C. Analysis of multiple matrix cracking in $[\pm\theta_m / 90_n]_s$ composite laminates, Part 1: In-plane stiffness properties. *Composites* 1992; **23**: 291-298.
6. Zhang J, Fan J & Soutis C. Analysis of multiple matrix cracking in $[\pm\theta_m / 90_n]_s$ composite laminates, Part 2: Development of transverse ply cracks. *Composites* 1992; **23**: 299-304.